

These use cases are intended to assist researchers. The instructions in the text are not legally binding. If you have any questions about data protection, copyright, or other legal aspects, make sure to contact the relevant offices at your university.

The use cases were developed collaboratively by the open-science teams at the Basel and Bern University Libraries and the data-protection officer of the University of Basel following a workshop on data protection and the anonymization of qualitative research data. People involved: Silke Bellanger, Christina Besmer, Danielle Kaufmann, Iris Lindenmann, Jennifer Morger, Gero Schreier. [The German version of the use cases](#) was published on zenodo in 2022. In 2024, the use cases were translated into English by Anthony Mahler.

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Using Repositories for Sensitive Data

Use Case

Ade Okafor is working on an SNSF-funded project that is conducting focus-group interviews with prisoners. The interviews are being recorded as videos in MP4 format and will then be transcribed. The interviewees (data subjects) have only granted permission to share the data on a repository under the condition of rigorous access restrictions with an application for use and a use agreement.

What are the options for sharing such data on a repository?

What are research-data repositories and what are the options for repositories?

Research-data [repositories](#) are online archives where research data and descriptive information (metadata) can be uploaded for the purpose of sharing them with other researchers and the public.

A distinction is often made between three types of repositories:

- generic repositories: researchers from all disciplines can upload data; examples: <https://www.zenodo.org>, <https://dataverse.harvard.edu>;
- institutional repositories: researchers from a specific institution (like a university) can upload data; example: <https://www.repository.cam.ac.uk> (University of Cambridge);
- discipline-specific repositories: researchers from a specific discipline or subject can upload data; examples: <https://www.swissubase.ch> (social sciences), <https://dasch.swiss> (humanities).

In most cases, it is recommended to share data on sub-

ject-specific repositories when possible, as they have a higher visibility among colleagues in your discipline. These repositories often also allow more detailed descriptions of datasets according to discipline-specific demands and standards.

What general legal rules and conditions apply when you use a repository?

The use of repositories constitutes a commissioned processing of data, in other words, the repository processes the data on behalf of the researchers and is only allowed to do so in the same manner as the researchers are permitted to do so under the applicable data-protection laws. This must be ensured by means of appropriate agreements. If the repository is additionally based abroad, then depositing the data there constitutes a data transfer abroad. In this case, you must check whether the level of data protection at the location of the repository corresponds to what is required in Switzerland or whether further contractual agreements are necessary. The federal government publishes a list on the equivalence of [other countries' data protection](#) to Switzerland's.

What should you pay attention to when choosing a repository for sensitive data?

It goes without saying that personal data can only be shared on a repository if the individuals concerned have given their consent. Before placing data on a repository, you should also contact the institution operating it for advice. It makes sense to seek such advice at an early stage of the project before data collection in order to ensure a smooth transfer of the data later on. Possible criteria for selecting a repository include the following:

- **Data security and reusability:** One of the most important criteria when data cannot be shared openly is whether a repository offers the necessary access and [reuse restrictions](#) (e.g., access only after registration, application for use, use agreement).
- **The location of the repository** (Switzerland or abroad); see the previous section on the general legal rules and conditions.
- **Accepted data types:** For researchers who work with personal data, it can be decisive whether a repository specializes in or even limits itself to qualitative or quantitative data. Some repositories only accept anonymized personal data.
- **Quality assurance:** At some repositories, expert staff check whether the submitted datasets and documentation are complete, whether the description and metadata comply with established standards, and so on. This is particularly common for repositories that specialize in certain disciplines and data types.
- **Other criteria:** Technical details—such as accepted file formats, maximum file sizes—or the requirements of research funding (e.g., the [SNSF's guidelines on data management plans](#), para. 5.1) can also play a role in the selection of a repository.

Where can I find suitable repositories?

The online registry www.re3data.org allows you to search for repositories by subject area. The individual entries in the database provide information on the operating institutions, the terms of service, and the technical standards employed. For an example of a Re3data entry, see <https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100010468>.

In the case of sensitive personal data, you should always request details about the terms of service and the modalities of use from the selected repository at an early stage.

What should you do if data may not be shared openly?

Whether personal data can be shared depends largely on the wording of the informed-consent document agreed to by the individuals concerned (data subjects). If they have not consented to allowing their data to be shared, then the data may not be shared. If they have not consented to open sharing (= publishing under an open license, e.g., CC BY, download option for all), then at least the metadata (= description of the dataset) can be shared publicly on a repository. The dataset itself can then be stored on the repository with restricted access or in a secure location outside the repository (for example, on a regularly maintained, restricted-access server without Internet access). In this case, the metadata should include a contact address for inquiries from other researchers as well as any conditions for possible reuse (e.g., use only after signing a [reuse agreement](#) and only for scientific purposes).

What do you need to consider when entering contact details on a repository?

If data cannot be shared openly, you should provide contact details (e.g., an email address) so that other researchers can write to obtain more information about the datasets in question. In this case, you should make sure to check and update the entered contact details regularly to ensure that the data can be reused long-term. Particularly if you have shared data on an institutional repository and then change universities, you should find someone to take over the tasks of communicating with researchers who request information and of granting them access.

What does that mean for this case?

At the start of the project, Ade Okafor reviews the offerings of various repositories and finally decides on SWISSUbase. SWISSUbase is a repository operated in Switzerland that specializes in data from the social sciences and related fields. It offers the possibility to describe datasets in detail and has a high level of visibility for researchers in Ade Okafor's discipline. It guarantees the quality of the uploaded data. It also meets the SNSF's criteria for data repositories. In addition to quantitative data, SWISSUbase also accepts qualitative data. The descriptions (metadata) of datasets are publicly accessible; the datasets themselves are only accessible after registering. The reuse of data is subject to an application for use and a use agreement. These security measures correspond to the security level specified in the informed-consent document for the video files.